

Local Government in Argentina

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Argentina

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Types of Local Governments

Argentina is a federal country consisting of 23 provinces and the Capital City of Buenos Aires as a federal district. Their autonomy is enshrined in the Constitution of 1853, which was last time reformed in 1994. According to the Federal Constitution, provinces can vote their own constitutions and laws. They have the power to elect their authorities and organize their own administrations, even in areas of justice and security. In addition, provinces have broad constitutional autonomy in fiscal and spending functions. A delineation of powers between central government and the provincial states is based on the general principle that all provinces have the power of those competences not expressly delegated in the Constitution to the federal state.

The third tier is composed of local governments. As the provinces have a political, administrative, judicial, and financial autonomy, the scope of municipal autonomy is determined by the province in which they are located. That translates into a wide range of definitions and configurations for local governments. Several municipal governments, depending on the provinces, have the authority to draft municipal charters (usually depending on the size of their populations). In some provinces, municipalities include only urban areas around cities, leaving rural areas under the jurisdiction of provincial governments. This translates into serious challenges for the delivery of social services. In others, municipal governments may include several cities and rural areas too.

Departments are an administrative division between provinces and municipalities, which do not have policy functions nor fiscal responsibilities. They mainly have a cadastral and statistical role, but in some provinces, they are also electoral districts to elect provincial representatives.

The adoption of federalism and a decentralized system of government that recognized autonomy to subnational units was the result of civil wars in the 1820s, after independence, and the only possible way to solve the political and economic conflicts in a country of enormous territorial extension.

Legal Status of Local Governments

Both the national Constitution, as amended in 1994, and most of the provincial constitutions explicitly recognize the autonomy of municipalities. According to Article 123 of the Argentine

Constitution, '[e]ach province dictates its own Constitution, in accordance with the provisions of Article 5 ensuring municipal autonomy and regulating its scope and content in the institutional, political, administrative, economic and financial order.' The sanction of several municipal charters (*cartas orgánicas municipales*) marks a progressive increase in the decision-making capacity of the municipalities. But this contrasts with limited administrative capacities to provide services (many of them decentralized at the provincial level) and scarce public resources and tax powers to finance their expenses (mostly concentrated at the national level).¹

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Although the Argentinian Constitution establishes a substantial autonomy for subnational tax powers, in practice the provinces have delegated large amounts of responsibility to the national government for the collection of revenue (income taxes, sales, special taxes and taxes on fuel). The resulting revenue concentration contrasts with a process of decentralization of expenditure whereby the responsibility for key social functions is in the provincial hands. The only activities that are the exclusive competence of the national authorities are those related to defense and foreign affairs. In the areas of economic affairs, public security, and social infrastructure, the national government shares responsibility with the provinces, while the latter have exclusive competence in primary and secondary education and local (municipal) organization and services. The Constitution defines a wide area of public services for which national and provincial authorities can participate in the legislation and provision of public services, although the tendency in the last two decades has been for the national government to decentralize direct administration of those functions to the provinces. Therefore, the provinces are currently in charge of most social expenditures (including basic education, health services, poverty programs, housing) and economic infrastructure. Despite this, the national government maintains a significant regulatory power in many of these areas and manages some programs within these sectors, such as social security, social programs for poorer households, and complementary educational programs that subsidize poorer schools.

Given this decentralization of spending and fiscal centralization, there is a high degree of vertical fiscal imbalance. Argentina addresses this large vertical fiscal imbalance through a complex system of intergovernmental transfers. The most important component of this system is the revenue sharing agreement (called *coparticipación*), which is the process by which part of the revenues collected by the central government are transferred to the provinces. Over time, the system has redistributed revenue from the richest central region to the most backward provinces in the northwest and northeast. It has also favored richer and low-density Patagonian provinces. Despite this, the system has corrected part of the large regional income

¹ Monica Iturburu, 'Municipios Argentinos: Potestades y restricciones constitucionales para un nuevo modelo de gestión local' (2nd ed, Instituto Nacional de la Administración Pública 2000) 33.

asymmetries among provinces in Argentina. We have to bear in mind that regional inequalities in Argentina are enormous. Formosa, for instance, has a GDP per capita more than 10 times lower than the City of Buenos Aires (2,256 versus USD 23,439). Although it has corrected regional income inequalities, the revenue transfer system has not had a substantial impact on provincial and local welfare indicators, as most social functions depend on the provinces (and are strongly correlated with provincial spending, particularly in social areas).

Political and Social Context in Argentina

The main parties that govern the provinces are the Justicialist Party (PJ), *Cambiamos*, which is the alliance governing the national government (formed by the Radical Civic Union, or UCR, Republican Proposal, or PRO, and other minor parties), and a constellation of minor parties, including the Socialist Party and provincial parties. *Cambiamos* governs four provinces (Buenos Aires, Corrientes, Jujuy and Mendoza) and the City of Buenos Aires. The PJ (in one of its several factions) governs 14 provinces (Catamarca, Chaco, Córdoba, Entre Ríos, Formosa, La Rioja, La Pampa, Salta, San Juan, San Luis, Santa Cruz, Tierra del Fuego, Tucumán, and Santiago del Estero). The socialists govern one province (Santa Fe) and provincial parties govern the other four provinces (Chubut, Misiones, Neuquén and Río Negro). Argentina has 1922 municipalities² governed by these and other national, provincial or local parties.

According to the last census, Argentina has 40,117,096 inhabitants, out of which more than 91 per cent (36,517,332) live in urban areas and the rest (3,599,764) in rural areas. More than 19 million live in 10 cities of more than 500,000 inhabitants, the largest being the metropolitan area of Buenos Aires (with 12,806,866 inhabitants and 31.9 per cent of the population).

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Iturburu M, 'Municipios Argentinos: Potestades y restricciones constitucionales para un nuevo modelo de gestión local' (2nd ed, Instituto Nacional de la Administración Pública 2000)

² Iturburu, 'Municipios Argentinos', above, 80.

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